

Music Initial Teacher Training Bursary Briefing Paper

October 2025

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Music Initial Teacher Training Bursary Briefing

Context

Since policy for teacher training bursaries and scholarships were highlighted as an educational priority in 2013¹, they have become a familiar part of the teacher education landscape. Music was included as a bursary until 2021, after which time its provision has been inconsistent. Table 1 sets out a brief history of the bursary for music teacher training, including the shifting requirements for receipt of the award:

Year	Bursary (£'s)	Notes (£'s)
2026-2027	0	Bursary unavailable
2025-2026	10,000	Bursary available to all with 1 st , 2:1, 2:2, PhD or Master's
2024-2025	10,000	Bursary available to all with 1 st , 2:1, 2:2, PhD or Master's
2023-2024	0	Bursary unavailable
2022-2023	0	Bursary unavailable
2021-2022	0	Bursary unavailable
2020-2021	9,000	Bursary available to all with 1 st , 2:1, 2:2, scholarship, doctoral degree or Master's
2019-2020	9,000	Bursary available to all with 1 st , 2:1, 2:2
2018-2019	4,000-9,000	9,000 available to all with 1 st or PhD. 4,000 available to all with 2:1 or Master's
2017-2018	4,000-9,000	9,000 available to all with 1 st or PhD. 4,000 available to all with 2:1 or Master's
2016-2017	4,000-9,000	9,000 available to all with 1 st or doctoral degree. 4,000 available to all with 2:1 or Master's
2015-2016	4,000-9,000	9,000 available to all with 1 st or PhD. 4,000 available to all with 2:1, Master's or 2:2
2014-2015	4,000-9,000	9,000 available to all with 1 st or equivalent. 4,000 available to all with 2:1 or equivalent

Table 1: A timeline of the DfE initial teacher training bursary for music²

¹ <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/bigger-bursaries-and-scholarships-to-attract-more-top-graduates-into-teaching>

² Sources for these figures are set out in full in table 3.

Bursary Impacts

Table 2 presents DfE datasets of DfE music trainee targets, the number of actual entrants and the bursary amount for that year:

Year	DfE Secondary Music Teacher Target	Secondary Music Teacher Trainees	Bursary Amount (£'s)
2014-2015	461	374	4,000-9,000
2015-2016	481	353	4,000-9,000
2016-2017	399	355	4,000-9,000
2017-2018	393	295	4,000-9,000
2018-2019	409	295	4,000-9,000
2019-2020	392	312	9,000
2020-2021	385	469	9,000
2021-2022	540	386	0
2022-2023	470	292	0
2023-2024	790	216	0
2024-2025	820	331	10,000
2025-2026	565	To be released Dec 2025	10,000
2026-2027	To be released April 2026	Not yet known	0

Table 2: Numbers for music teacher targets, trainees and bursary amounts 2014-2027³

Commentary

Our analysis of the figures in tables 1 and 2 would suggest that sustained bursary funding for initial teacher training in music leads to more stable recruiting, helping to minimise gaps between recruitment targets and trainee entrants. For instance, in 2016-2017, 355 trainees were recruited against a target of 399, and in 2017-2018, 295 trainees were recruited against a target of 393. In years when no bursary is offered, the gap appears to widen, with 386 trainees recruited against a target of 540 in the 2021 intake, 292 recruited against a target of 470 in the 2022 intake, 216 against a target of 790 in the 2023 intake, and 331 recruited against a target of 820 in the 2024 intake. To put it another way, when the bursary

³ Sources: Column 1: table_1_subject_characteristics initial-teacher-training-census-2024-25. Available at: Initial Teacher Training Census, Academic year 2024/25 - Explore education statistics - GOV.UK Column https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a8052d440f0b62305b8a7a7/ITT_CENSUS_SFR_46_2015_to_2016.pdf, https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a8099f6e5274a2e87dbabe3/ITT_Census_1617_SFR_Final.pdf, https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a81e6d1e5274a2e8ab5670e/SFR68_2017_Text.pdf, https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5bfe67fbed915d11878d7e42/ITT_Census_2018_to_2019_main_text.pdf ITT Census 1718 SFR Template

on offer is in a state of flux, so music teacher recruitment seems to also be unstable and highly variable.

In addition, it is unclear how decisions about the music bursary can be made when the secondary Initial Teacher Training Census is not due for publication until December 2025, and the target for secondary music teacher trainee recruitment will not be decided until April 2026. As the bursary appears to have a significant impact on teacher training numbers, the links between targets and entrants needs not to be readily dismissed. The lack of a bursary in 2026-2027, only two years after its re-introduction is therefore a cause of real concern. This is particularly relevant as we know from DfE figures that a lack of funding is likely to negatively impact the numbers of music trainees, and ultimately the number of music teachers enabling musical development for young people in our school classrooms.

Questions for consideration

1. What rationale has been used to decide the bursary amounts for the coming year, especially when music is already under severe strain in our schools, and has been debated in parliament frequently in recent months?
2. How can we be sure that the lack of bursary is unlikely to create further barriers to music teacher recruitment, particularly at a time when access to music teacher training is essential to maintain teacher supply in our schools?
3. How can bursary amounts be set before teacher training recruitment targets?
4. The state of flux of bursaries for music teacher training, places initial teacher training providers in a challenging situation for their own course planning. What reassurances can be given about the long-term commitment of preserving and expanding young people's entitlement to music in school?

What could be done?

Recommendations to address this instability include:

1. Undertaking to preserve annual music teacher training bursaries, and committing to do this for the next 10 years, thereby enabling teacher training providers to invest in long-term planning and provision. (There is precedent for this, as the bursary was provided continuously for music teacher trainees for 6 years, between 2014-2020.)
2. Placing value on music in school through policy statements which undertake to adequately resource music teacher recruitment.
3. Addressing the gap between music teacher recruitment and music teacher supply shortfalls, by emphasising the central place of music teacher bursaries in all public engagements, rather than discussing potential awards in subjects such as science and maths alone⁴.

⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/pupils-to-benefit-from-more-specialist-teachers-in-classrooms>

Year	Data Source
2026	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/funding-initial-teacher-training-itt/funding-initial-teacher-training-itt-academic-year-2026-to-2027#postgraduate-bursaries-and-scholarships
2025	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/funding-initial-teacher-training-itt/funding-initial-teacher-training-itt-academic-year-2025-to-2026
2024	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/funding-initial-teacher-training-itt/funding-initial-teacher-training-itt-academic-year-2024-to-2025
2023	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/funding-initial-teacher-training-itt/funding-initial-teacher-training-itt-academic-year-2023-to-2024
2022	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/initial-teacher-training-itt-bursary-funding-manual/initial-teacher-training-bursaries-funding-manual-2022-to-2023-academic-year#:~:text=Undergraduate%20bursary,2022%20to%202023%20academic%20year
2021	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/initial-teacher-training-itt-bursary-funding-manual/initial-teacher-training-bursaries-funding-manual-2021-to-2022-academic-year#:~:text=Undergraduate%20bursary,2021%20to%202022%20academic%20year
2020	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/initial-teacher-training-itt-bursary-funding-manual/initial-teacher-training-bursaries-funding-manual-2020-to-2021-academic-year#:~:text=A%20training%20bursary%20for%20final,2020%20to%202021%20academic%20year
2019	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/initial-teacher-training-itt-bursary-funding-manual/initial-teacher-training-bursaries-funding-manual-2019-to-2020-academic-year#:~:text=A%20training%20bursary%20for%20final,2019%20to%202020%20academic%20year
2018	https://www.gov.uk/guidance/funding-initial-teacher-training-itt-academic-year-2018-to-19
2017	https://www.gov.uk/guidance/funding-initial-teacher-training-itt-academic-year-2017-to-18
2016	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/further-education-initial-teacher-training-bursary-2016-to-2017
2015	https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a82b1a8e5274a2e8ab58db4/170329_Training_Bursary_Guide_AY_2016_17_Final.pdf
2014	https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5a82053540f0b6230269a685/140115_Training_Bursary_Guide_AY_1415_FINAL_V1.5_NR.pdf

Table 3: Sources for figures in table 1